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UCO DWM1001: A tool for managing and processing the UWB DWM1001-DEV development board

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ABSTRACT

UCO DWM1001 is a free software developed to facilitate the work with DWM1001-DEV, one of the most widely used ultra-wideband (UWB) development boards. The software is designed to process, display, and store the relevant information of a UWB network system. The developed tool enables the user to manage the device transparently, establishing a connection, managing communication, and providing a range of features that facilitate the work and study of UWB technology. Communication is based on terminal emulation, whereby received messages are processed in accordance with their properties, the operating mode set, or the application tool used. The software's principal functions comprise real-time data visualisation, data saving, and an integrated terminal emulator for direct communication with the DWM1001-DEV development board. The tool, developed using the Qt framework, is intended to provide researchers with a straightforward method to utilise and assess the performance of DWM1001-DEV in diverse indoor settings, as well as to construct a basic UWB positioning network. Two illustrative examples are presented to demonstrate the capabilities of UCO DWM1001 software.

1. Metadata

Nr	Code metadata description	
C1	Current code version	v1.0.0
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/AntonioRuizR/UCO-DWM-GUI
C3	Permanent link to executables of this version	https://github.com/AntonioRuizR/UCO-DWM-GUI/releases
C4	Legal code license	GNU General Public License (GPL) v3
C5	Code versioning system used	git
C6	Software code languages, tools and services used	C++
C7	Compilation requirements, operating environments and dependencies	Qt 6.6.1, MinGW 11.2.0 64-bit, qmake
C8	If available, link to developer documentation/manual	https://github.com/AntonioRuizR/UCO-DWM-GUI/blob/main/User%20Guide.pdf
C9	Support email for questions	mario.ruz@uco.es

2. Motivation and significance

Ultra-wideband (UWB) technology is renowned for its capacity to provide the distance between two or more devices with remarkable accuracy [1]. This technology has an application range that can extend up to hundreds of metres, utilising ranging methodologies such as time-of-flight or two-way ranging [2]. Its low power consumption and suitability for high-rate data transmission [3] make it an ideal choice for indoor or short-range applications. For the DWM1001-DEV development board, the distance between devices is estimated using the Round-Trip Time (RTT) based Two-Way Ranging (TWR) algorithm, which calculates the delay of a radio signal from a transmitter to a receiver. This algorithm is appropriate due to the high time resolution of UWB radio signals [4].

The range of applications for this radio technology extends beyond the simple location application. For instance, in a smart warehouse logistics implementation, UWB technology is employed for tracking robots, automated guided vehicles (AGVs), or different products [5]. This technology is also employed in diverse fields, including medicine, as evidenced by studies [6] and [7], or in the analysis of the degradation of

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equipment with the objective of optimizing efficiency and cost. This latter study, for instance, employs UWB antennas to analyse the deflection of wind turbines with UWB sensors placed on the blades [8]. Other potential applications include industrial safety, due to the straightforwardness of UWB technology in estimating distances and positions in indoor settings. Within this context, from original Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) based implementations to most recent UWB tags, reviews are provided in several papers, in which some experimental tests are carried out in this field [9] [10], and [11]. In relation to the subject of this paper, it is essential to have appropriate software for the simulation [12], management, and testing [13] of the devices that are required in these applications, in order to facilitate further analysis and development.

In the case of DWM1001-DEV, the available software is limited to performing a network configuration [14] or an obsolete gateway implementation that requires a specific single-board computer [15]. Additionally, the main commercially available software with similar functionalities is proprietary [16–18].

The DWM1001-DEV is designed to evaluate the features and performance of the DWM1001C UWB transceiver module, facilitating both technology analysis and more advanced implementations [19]. This paper presents a tool that is capable of obtaining and processing distance measurements and the positioning of UWB devices in a network. Moreover, the software facilitates the plotting of these values in real time, along with several additional features. In this manner, the user can examine the system performance in a variety of UWB applications, utilising integrated tools such as data representation, statistical analysis, and real-time distance recording for subsequent post-processing. It should be noted that the proposed application approach is extensible for similar modules.

3. Software description

3.1. Software architecture

UCO DWM1001 is an application developed in the C++ programming language using the Qt framework [20]. It is released under the terms of the GNU General Public License v3.0 [21]. The objective of this software is to provide a series of tools to manage the DWM1001-DEV development board and process its data. The aforementioned tools are integrated into a single application, which enables the user to conduct an initial analysis of the performance of the UWB technology incorporated in these devices. Moreover, the software enables the user to post-process the information received, allowing for the recording of distance or position data.

Its graphical interface has been developed with several main features, including the real-time graphical representation and recording of data, the application of a media filter, the activation of a General-Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) on the development board when certain setpoint values are exceeded, and the calculation of statistical measurements.

UCO DWM1001 is operated by establishing a USB connection with the DWM1001-DEV development board. The communication with the module is conducted via the 'UART shell' mode, which is included in the PANS 2.0 firmware of the DWM1001-DEV [14].

This communication mode enables users to establish a connection to the device and manage communication via ASCII commands. This facilitates the transmission of commands and the reception of data in a straightforward manner. As the communication is wired and utilises the Universal Asynchronous Receiver-Transmitter (UART) external access Application Programming Interface (API), the application is ready for use once the development board is connected [22].

Each received message is processed based on the information that it contains and the selected operation mode. This encompasses module configuration, module information, distance or position data reception. Similarly, UCO DWM1001 manages the commands to be sent in

response to the user's request. The available commands for UART shell mode can be found in the DWM1001 documentation [14] and a further architecture explanation by means of code documentation is also available in the software repository.

In summary, a basic UWB positioning network based on the DWM1001-DEV device has two modes of operation:

- Tag: Mobile device that calculates the distance between it and the anchors in the network. If possible, the position in the network is estimated.
- Anchor: Fixed module whose position is known.

A minimum of two DWM1001-DEV modules for distance measurement is required. For position processing, a minimum of three anchors and one tag is needed, calculating the distance from the tag to each anchor, and estimating its position relative to the reference system created by the modules configured as anchors using the trilateration algorithm [23].

The software has been developed to operate in two principal modes. The first mode plots the distances from the DWM1001-DEV connected to the tool to a maximum of four devices. This number of distance measurements, accessible via wired communication, is limited by the firmware [22]. Furthermore, a second operational mode is available in which the position of a tag within a network comprising a minimum of three anchors is obtained and processed. This position is either directly obtained from the tag or indirectly via a passive anchor acting as a listener, which receives the data and transmits it to the PC via the USB connection. In this latter case, the moving tag is not required to be connected to the PC. Fig. 1 presents a simplified illustration of the communication process, operational procedures, and principal functions in this application.

The graphical representation has been implemented using the QCustomPlot widget library, an open-source Qt C++ widget for plotting data in real time [24].

3.2. Software functionalities

To facilitate the use of DWM1001-DEV development boards for receiving, processing, saving, and analysing estimated distances and positions, a set of functionalities has been developed. These functionalities are itemized below.

3.2.1. DWM1001-DEV device configuration

The application enables a basic configuration of the DWM1001-DEV development board, thereby avoiding the necessity for supplementary software to establish a UWB positioning network. The developed functions facilitate basic functions, such as the configuration of the network, operation mode, reset, and factory reset of the board. If more sophisticated options are required, this can be accomplished through the application terminal emulator discussed in section 2.2.8.

Once the DWM1001-DEV board is connected via USB and the connection is established through the application, the interface enters the command interpreter mode (UART shell) of the development board and establishes the initial GPIOs configuration. After configuring the GPIOs, a command is sent, and the information related to the connected module is obtained by splitting and analysing the message. This information includes the operating mode, network ID, and firmware version. At this juncture, both the DWM1001-DEV board and the application await instructions.

Additionally, the UCO DWM1001-DEV permits the configuration of various application aspects, including language, distance and position graph options, or the name and folder of the generated comma-separated-values (csv) file.

3.2.2. Distance and position graphical representation

As illustrated in the main window in Fig. 2(a), one of the principal

Fig. 1. Operation and communication scheme between DWM1001-DEV and UCO DWM-1001.

functions of the developed application is the capacity to represent the distance of a module configured as a tag up to a maximum of four anchors in a graphical format. In this operational mode, the net anchors are not required to be fixed in a single position. As an additional tool, it is possible to apply a media filter in real time to each of the measured distances. This is useful for the avoidance of outliers in the performance of perimeter-related applications. Similarly, another tab, displayed in Fig. 2(b), allows the user to visualise the positioning of a tag module within a network comprising these devices. In this operation mode, fixed anchors are required to estimate the tag's position. The development of both implementations was made possible by the QCustomPlot libraries for Qt, which enable the real-time graphical representation of data.

3.2.3. Export received data

In order to facilitate the post-processing of experimental tests carried out with the tool, a feature has been implemented to store the data received from the connected device. This tool records all the information needed to analyse the results in a csv text file. The resulting file contains the index of the data received, the date and time, the distance or position data and the state of the selected GPIO.

3.2.4. Statistics

A statistical calculation window has been implemented. The window displays the following calculations: mean, mode, standard deviation, maximum, minimum, range, and percentiles.

3.2.5. Data history representation

To supplement the main graphical representation window, the application provides an additional function that displays all the received distance or position data. This allows the user to observe the complete set of the received data from the beginning of the test, select a graph and a range within the measurements taken, and obtain some statistics on the selected range. This feature is shown in Fig. 3 with the distance display of four devices.

3.2.6. Perimeter distinction

The possibility to evaluate the accuracy of the measurement, as well as the response time of the activation of a selected GPIO, has been added.

This is achieved by evaluating a defined perimeter so that, if the distance obtained is higher or lower than a defined value, the activation of one of the GPIOs present on the DWM1001-DEV development board is triggered. This function applies both to distance measurement and to the three axes of a module position estimation.

3.2.7. GPIO management

It is possible to configure the activation of several GPIOs of the connected module independently of the other functions mentioned above. If required, a timer can be assigned for the activation or deactivation of the selected GPIO.

3.2.8. Terminal emulator

The included terminal window allows to visualise the communication between the PC running the application and the development board connected through the UART shell mode. It also allows any command to be sent to the module via the command interpreter mode.

4. Illustrative examples

To demonstrate the use of the tool, two examples are shown below, both for distance measurement and position display. Additionally, perimeter distinction and postprocessing functions applicable to both modes are discussed.

4.1. Distance mode

In this scenario, if there is at least one initiating anchor within the same network, selecting the distance mode and activating the data reception will result in the distance between the two modules being displayed in the corresponding window. In the event of additional modules being incorporated into the network, each of the existing distances will be displayed up to a maximum of four. Furthermore, the option to activate the media filter, the alarm assigned to a GPIO, the data recording, the statistics request or the complete data history display will be available. Fig. 2(a) illustrates an example of a distance query for a set of four other devices. In this mode, the distance measured is displayed with the corresponding ID of each device in the panel below the graph. If

a. Distance mode representation of four distances, x-axis (s), y-axis (m).

b. Position mode representation (red tag) with perimeter distinction enabled. Coloured rectangle is the allowed area and blue points are the fixed anchor nodes.

Fig. 2. Graphic representation feature in the Main Window of UCO DWM1001.

Fig. 3. Data history representation of four distances.

the media filter is enabled, its value is displayed below the real-time value received.

4.2. Positioning mode

Once the UWB sensor network has been created and the tool has been configured in Positioning mode, the same initial steps as in Distance mode are carried out to request the display in Positioning mode. To graphically display the location of the tag device in real time, data

reception is initiated, where the position is displayed in the pertinent tab. In this mode, the axes and the position of the fixed anchors in the network can be manually edited. Data recording, media filtering, and the rest of the developed functions have been implemented in this mode. An example of the use of this mode is illustrated in Fig. 2(b).

Fig. 4. Alarm activation in a configuration of one distance estimation.

4.3. Additional tools

4.3.1. Perimeter distinction

It is possible to establish an alarm to a defined perimeter in terms of distance or positioning. A set of defined limits will trigger the activation of a selected GPIO. Fig. 4 shows an example of the alarm configuration and activation for a distance measurement of 70 cm. If the obtained distance exceeds the limit set, a warning is displayed on the screen and the selected GPIO is set to 1. This event is also recorded in the csv file.

4.3.2. Data save and post-processing

As discussed above, the position or distance data stored using the csv data storage feature can be analysed using suitable processing software, such as MATLAB or the open-source alternative Scilab, to perform the required statistical calculations and to produce the desired graphical representation of the data set as shown in Fig. 5. In this way, in addition to the processing performed by the UCO DWM1001, the raw data is made available for further analysis. Some examples of post-processing scripts are included in the GitHub repository.

5. Impact

With the increasing interest and development of UWB technology in recent years, new applications and devices have emerged that incorporate this technology due to its high accuracy in estimating distance and

position. Among the test and development devices incorporating this technology is the DWM1001-DEV development board, which has its own considerable user community [25].

As mentioned above, and to the authors' knowledge, there is currently no application that allows direct work, managing communication with the device, allowing the user to visualize in real-time distance and position estimation or to record the data received. The software available from the DWM1001-DEV company, Qorvo, consists of two different software applications, an Android OS application that only allows the user to configure a positioning network and visualise the position of a tag in real-time via a Bluetooth connection, and a web manager in a gateway configuration that receives position data using an MQTT connection protocol. This method is limited because, to achieve this configuration, a development board must be connected exclusively to a Raspberry Pi 3B, precluding the use of other single-board computer models.

Accordingly, this application has been developed to facilitate the user's operation of the DWM1001-DEV, providing a tool with multiple functions for the evaluation of the UWB technology implemented in this device, both in real-time and in subsequent data processing. The application enables the user to view the two aforementioned operating modes. It comprises a window for a graphical display of the distance and another section for displaying the position of the tag on a two-dimensional plane. The tool also incorporates the capability to set up alarms that alert the user in the event of being in a position or distance exceeding predefined thresholds, thereby activating a previously selected GPIO pin. Additionally, a media filter can be configured and activated at the user's request, with the option to link it to the activation of the alarm. Another significant feature of the application is the ability to record data received in a text file in csv format, allowing for subsequent processing. In summary, this tool facilitates the user to manage, visualise and process the information received in the UWB network. Furthermore, direct communication with the board via ASCII commands is also implemented.

6. Conclusions and future directions

The objective of this software is to facilitate basic operations associated with the DWM1001-DEV development board for UWB applications. To this end, a tool has been developed in C++ using the Qt framework, which offers a range of functions for processing the data received by the device.

The primary objective of future work is to circumvent the constraints imposed by the manufacturer firmware, including the limitations on the collection of distances between pairs of nodes and the number of anchor nodes considered per tag. Once all pairwise distances can be collected, users will be able to implement custom localisation algorithms. As the provided software is open source, any interested party can propose modifications or improvements.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Antonio Ruiz: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Juan Garrido:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Investigation. **Francisco Vázquez:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Mario L. Ruz:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 5. Data post-processing example of a positioning test.

Data availability

Code and some example data generated with the application are available in the GitHub repository.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.softx.2024.101848](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2024.101848).

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